
Research

A Study on the Influencing Factors of Financial Service Cooperation between China and Turkmenistan

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Abstract: This paper studies the financial cooperation between China and Turkmenistan in the context of the "the Belt and Road" through quantitative analysis. First, the development status of financial cooperation between China and Turkmenistan in the context of the "the Belt and Road" is described through three parts: the current situation of macroeconomic development between China and Turkmenistan, the current situation of import and export trade in financial services, and the current situation of financial cooperation; Then, the analysis of the influencing factors on the development of financial cooperation between China and Turkmenistan is elaborated through three parts: indicator selection and data sources, empirical testing, and empirical analysis. The empirical analysis results show that the per capita financial wealth of Turkmenistan and the total financial wealth of Turkmenistan have a promoting effect on financial cooperation between China and Turkmenistan, while the per capita financial wealth of China has a relatively small impact on financial cooperation between China and Turkmenistan; The explanation of financial cooperation in China and Turkmenistan ranges from large to small: per capita financial wealth in Turkmenistan, financial cooperation in China and Turkmenistan, total financial wealth in Turkmenistan, and per capita financial wealth in China. Finally, this article proposes some policy suggestions: to improve the development of Turkmenistan's financial industry and promote the increase of total wealth; Improving the per capita financial wealth of Turkmenistan and focusing on per capita income development; Optimize the allocation ratio of investment financial assets in China and promote the growth of per capita financial wealth in China.

Keywords: China; Kazakhstan; Financial cooperation,

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Introduction

Turkmenistan's per capita GDP in 2022 will be more than US\$10,000, the highest among the five Central Asian countries. China launched the "One Belt, One Road" initiative in 2013, using the land-based "Silk Road" and the maritime "Silk Road" to provide infrastructure construction investment for countries along the route. This is a good opportunity for Turkmenistan. China's infrastructure construction capital and technology reserves are relatively abundant, so Turkmenistan can use China's relevant capital and technology to promote the development of its own infrastructure construction. At the same time, China can also effectively drive the vitality of local economic development.

In the context of the "Belt and Road" initiative, China and Turkmenistan have good cooperation opportunities. Both China and Turkmenistan are land territories, so in the process of economic development, cooperation and trade between the two countries are more convenient, which is beneficial to both countries. The development of financial trade will also have a promoting effect. China has established the Asian Infrastructure Investment Bank based on the "Belt and Road" initiative, which plays an important role in the cooperation and development of the financial industry between China and other countries. Only by continuously improving China's financial influence can we increase financial cooperation with other countries. possibility. Turkmenistan also attaches great importance to the tertiary industry in the process of economic development. Finance is the core of the tertiary industry. Therefore, the future financial cooperation between China and Turkmenistan will rely on the continuous and in-depth development of the economic transformation of the two countries.

Research Methodology

This article is elaborated in four parts, and the specific research content is as follows.

Chapter One Introduction. This chapter is elaborated through four parts: research background, research significance, research status, research content and methods.

Chapter 2: Analysis of the current situation of financial services trade between China and Turkmenistan. This chapter elaborates on the current status of macroeconomic development between China and Turkmenistan, the current status of financial services industry development, and the current status of financial services import and export trade between China and Turkmenistan.

Chapter 3: Analysis of factors affecting the import and export trade of financial services between China and Turkmenistan. This chapter explains it through three parts: indicator selection and data sources, empirical testing, and empirical analysis.

Chapter 4: Summary and suggestions. This chapter puts forward targeted policy suggestions through the conclusions of the empirical analysis, such as: improving the development of Turkmenistan's financial industry and promoting the increase of total wealth; increasing Turkmenistan's per capita financial wealth and focusing on the development of per capita income; optimizing the financial assets of China's investment The allocation ratio will promote the growth of China's per capita financial wealth.

Literature research

Through the literature research method, we can better understand the relevant research conducted by different scholars in the field of the "One Belt, One Road" initiative and the financial cooperation between China and Turkmenistan. Standing on the shoulders of previous scholars can better analyze and elaborate on this article, and effectively improve the depth of this article's research.

quantitative analysis

This article will use the VAR model to analyze the influencing factors on financial cooperation between China and Turkmenistan, put forward targeted policy suggestions through the results of empirical analysis, and effectively help China and Turkmenistan develop better in the field of financial cooperation.

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